

JOB SCHEDULING TO MINIMIZE MAKESPAN AT SMES OF BATIK INDUSTRY

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Abstract

In this modern era and the high competitiveness in batik industry, SMEs are required to improve their production and services by enhancing the engine utility and accuracy in the production completion to meet the schedule at batik industry. The purpose of this research is to minimize the processing time (makespan) of batik industry production process. The proposed scheduling method consist of Campbell, Dudek and Smith (CDS), Nawaz, Ensore and HAM (NEH), and Theory of Constraint (TOC). CDS methods combine the sorted time from the smallest to the largest based on the Johnson's rule. NEH heuristic sorted the job in two different sequences (J1-J2 and J2-J1), selected the smallest makespan and carried it on until the n jobs. TOC method have function to identify an obstacle which happened on each process that did in the company. Those methods applied which have result in different job sequences and has the smallest makespan for NEH method. NEH method is a method with the best makespan time which is 3316.03 minutes. By implement NEH method it can be thrift up to 2.42%. Then, there are disadvantageous for the unfulfilled product up to IDR 9,539,250.00. Therefore, it can be concluded, there are need overtime for the workers while finished the target which spend overtime cost up to IDR 4,375,000.00.

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.2525474

I. Introduction

In this modern era, SMEs of industry batik had many orders from variant product. Most of the customer needs the quick service for the finish product. For on time and an optimal product completion is the goal that should be achieved where the solution is the main thing by maximizing the schedule effectively. Taking the schedule decision should be based on several important criteria such as minimize idle time, total set up time, work in process inventory, and maximize the machine utility. Determination of the schedules that meet all of the above criteria are very difficult. To simplify the problem, there are use criteria which can represent from the above criteria. The criteria are minimizing makespan which is minimize the overall length of operation in the process, minimize makespan which tend to produce low idle time, low semi-finished inventory, and high machine utilities [1] .

In this research implement several methods such as Campbell, Dudek and Smith (CDS), Nawaz, Ensore and HAM (NEH), and Theory of Constraint (TOC). Based on the data obtained from the research result conducted at PT. Traingle Motorindo for scheduling production by using CDS method known that the scheduling to be applied in PT. Triangle Motorindo Semarang had total makespan 23.1 hours and efficiency around 35.26% [2].

Rather than that, there are research about scheduling using NEH and Ignall-Scharge method at CV. Bestone Indonesia has been using intuitive methods only. This research concern on the

smallest makespan value. The minimum makespan of scheduling on NEH and Ignall-Scharge has the same time 389052.25 seconds but has different job sequencing of NEH with the sequence 3-1-4-2 and Ignall-Scharge sequence with the scheduling sequence 3-4-1-2. The makespan value among both of these methods has difference time of 64.27 seconds with intuitive scheduling applied by the company [3].(1)

In the research scheduling using NEH and CDS methods was done by the company that previously applied the method of First Come First Service (FCFS) scheduling. The type of company which used in this research is flow shop. This research conducted has a goal to save the production cost rather than just concern on makespan. The calculation result was obtained if CDS method has 31 hours of makespan while NEH has makespan 39 hours. CDS method has the smallest makespan even there are high production cost because there are implement overtime system, while NEH method has the smaller production cost. By using CDS method, the company saving the production cost for Rp 10.433.190,03 while by implement NEH method, the company saving up to Rp 8.574.277,46 [4] (2)

II. BASIC THEORY

A. *Campbell, Dudek and Smith (CDS)*

Campbell, Dudek and Smith (CDS) method was developed by H.G Campbell, R.A. Dudek, and M.L. Smith based on algorithm Johnson [5]. Basically, this method can solve the problem of two machines of flow shop by dividing the m machine into two groups, then by sorting the job from both of machines which used algorithm Johnson. After obtaining as much as m-1 alternatives, there will be selected for the smallest makespan sequence.

The calculation of Campbell, Dudek and Smith (CDS) method can be did by several stages as follows [6]:

- 1) Take the first sequence ($k=1$). For all of the jobs, looking for the minimum price of $t_{i,1}^*$ and $t_{i,2}^*$ which is the processing time on the first out of the second machines.
- 2) If the minimum time can be gain on the first machine (example: $t_{i,1}$), then positioning on the beginning sequence, then if the minimum time can be gain on the second machines (example: $t_{i,2}$), those jobs can be positioned on the last sequence.
- 3) Move those jobs only from the list and the sequence. If there are still exist the remnant job, repeat again the first step, otherwise if there are didn't exist the remnant job, the sequencing process have been done.

B. *Nawaz, Enscore and HAM (NEH)*

Nawaz, Enscore and HAM (NEH) method was develop and used in the processing time for respectively job and to reduce time from the production. The steps of using NEH comes from heuristics which are:

- 1) Sequencing the job based on Short Processing Time (SPT) rule.
- 2) Then start by trying those sequence ($j1, j2$) and ($j2, j1$). Calculate makespan from both of the sequence and choose the smallest ($j2, j1$).
- 3) Calculation will be continued based on the next job ($j3$). Then calculate the makespan from three of sequences which are ($j3, j2, j1$), ($j2, j3, j1$), ($j2, j1, j3$) and choose the smallest sequence.
- 4) Continued the calculation to get the the smallest sequence [7] (2)

C. *THEORY OF CONSTRAINT (TOC)*

Theory of Constraints is one of management philosophy based on achievement principles which concern on continuous improvement through concerning on the constraints system. In the production scheduling, TOC has role as a synchronization of all sub-systems. Synchronization means flow rate production setting from each of sub system with the purpose to avoid the excessive burden on work station which had the lowest capacity as the constraint station [8]. This

will simplify the scheduling process because it can sufficient for scheduling the station constraint and the other station will adjust. TOC can be applied to identify an obstacle which happened on each process that did in the company. In several research using Theory of Constraint (TOC) approach which are Sihite (2002) explain that scheduling using Theory of Constraint concept which can decrease bottleneck in the production line. Patterson dan Bob Harmel (2005) has research in the scheduling using Drum-Buffer-Rope that can increase throughput and significant income [9] (3)

TOC can be applied to identify the constraint on each process which did by the company. In this case, TOC was implemented during identify the obstacle on scheduling process of batik industry at Yogyakarta.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This research is focused in the scheduling. Data collection is done by observation for several data such as the amount of machine, the processing time, type of product. This research is done in three stages, i.e. calculation of CDS, calculation of NEH, and compare the makespan of CDS with NEH then will be execute using TOC.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this research at one of batik industry SMEs in Yogyakarta, there are several problems which the long shipment and high cost of production are. Therefore, to minimize the long shipment to the customer as the researcher we would like to solve the problem by make the scheduling using several methods such as CDS and NEH. In the below is the basic data which will be processed by the researcher.

Table 1. Basic Data

Process	Machine Quantity	Duration (minutes)	
		Dress	Shirt
Pre-cutting	1	0.583	0.583
Cutting	4	8	5
Sewing	22	120	100
Obras	4	10	-
Zig-zag	2	6	3
QC	2	2.5	3
Itik-itik	1	2	3
Buttoning	2	20.1	19
Ironing	2	6.35	2.17
Packing	1	1	1

Table 2. Basic Data

Product	Order Quantity	Type
Product 1	56	dress
Product 2	47	shirt
Product 3	39	dress
Product 4	36	dress
Product 5	23	shirt
Product 6	22	dress
Product 7	20	shirt
Product 8	18	dress
Product 9	17	shirt
Product 10	17	shirt

4.1 CDS Result

In the below is the result of CDS calculation about machining processing time.

Table 3. Machining Calculation of CDS

Job (Product)	Job 1	Job 2	Job 3	Job 4	Job 5
Machine 1	56	47	39	36	56

Machine 2	112	60	80	72	112
Machine 3	360	300	240	240	360
Machine 4	140	-	-	-	140
Machine 5	168	-	120	108	168
Machine 6	70	72	50	45	70
Machine 7	112	141	78	72	112
Machine 8	562.8	456	402	361.8	562.8
Machine 9	177.8	52.08	127	114.3	177.8
Machine 10	56	47	39	36	56

Table 4. Machining Calculation of CDS

Job (Product)	Job 6	Job 7	Job 8	Job 9	Job 10
Machine 1	22	20	18	17	17
Machine 2	48	25	40	25	25
Machine 3	120	100	120	100	100
Machine 4	-	-	-	-	-
Machine 5	-	30	54	-	-
Machine 6	27.5	30	22.5	27	27
Machine 7	44	60	36	51	51
Machine 8	221.1	190	180.9	171	171
Machine 9	69.85	21.7	57.15	19.53	19.53
Machine 10	22	20	18	17	17

According to the above calculation, then the researcher can determine the scheduling sequences of CDS method which consist of 4 types of scheduling job sequences:

For the 1st scheduling sequence there will be job 10-job 9-job 7-job 5-job 8-job 6-job 4-job 2-job 3-job 1 which spend 3398.4 minutes.

For the 2nd scheduling sequence consist of job 9-job 10-job 8-job 7-job 6-job 5-job 4-job 3-job 2-job 1 which spend 3398.4 minutes.

For the 3rd scheduling sequence consist of job 1-job 3-job 4-job 6-job 2-job 8-job 5-job 7-job 9-job 10 which spend 3999.13 minutes.

For the last sequence consist of job 1-job 3-job 2-job 4-job 6-job 5-job 8-job 7-job 9-job 10 which spend 3999.13 minutes.

Among 4 types of scheduling job sequences, there are the smallest makespan up to 3398.4 which had 2 types job sequences which are be job 10-job 9-job 7-job 5-job 8-job 6-job 4-job 2-job 3-job 1 and 9-job 10-job 8-job 7-job 6-job 5-job 4-job 3-job 2-job 1.

4.2 NEH Result

In the below is the result of NEH calculation which shown their own scheduling job sequences which are:

For the 1st scheduling sequence, there will be job 10-job 6-job 4-job 8-job 7-job 5-job 2-job 3-job 1-job 9 which spend 3359.3 minutes.

For the 2nd scheduling sequence, there will be job 10-job 1-job 6-job 4-job 8-job 7-job 5-job 2-job 3-job 9 which spend 3845.13 minutes.

For the 3rd scheduling sequence, there will be job 10-job 6-job 1-job 4-job 8-job 7-job 5-job 2-job 3-job 9 which spend 3701.03 minutes.

For the 4th scheduling sequence, there will be job 10-job 6-job 4-job 1-job 8-job 7-job 5-job 2-job 3-job 9 which spend 3579.23 minutes.

For the 5th scheduling sequence, there will be job 10-job 6-job 4-job 8-job 1-job 7-job 5-job 2-job 3-job 9 which spend 3518.33 minutes.

For the 6th scheduling sequence, there will be job 10-job 6-job 4-job 8-job 7-job 1-job 5-job 2-job 3-job 9 which spend 3428.33 minutes.

For the 7th scheduling sequence, there will be job 10-job 6-job 4-job 8-job 7-job 5-job 1-job 2-job 3-job 9 which spend 3400.33 minutes.

For the 8th scheduling sequence, there will be job 10-job 6-job 4-job 8-job 7-job 5-job 2-job 1-job 3-job 9 which spend 3316.03 minutes.

For the 9th scheduling sequence, there will be job 10-job 6-job 4-job 8-job 7-job 5-job 2-job 3-job 9-job 1 which spend 3513.3 minutes.

For the 10th scheduling sequence, there will be job 1-job 10-job 6-job 4-job 8-job 7-job 5-job 2-job 3-job 9 which spend 3999.13 minutes.

According to the above job sequences, it can be concluded that in the 8th job sequences, there had the smallest makespan up to 3316.03 minutes. Therefore, there are the selected completion time in NEH method that shown in Table 3.

Table 5. Selected Completion Time

Job 10	Job 6	Job 4	Job 8	Job 7
Completion Time				
17	39	75	93	113
42	90	162	202	227
142	262	502	622	722
142	262	502	622	722
142	262	610	676	752
169	289.5	655	698.5	782
220	333.5	727	763	842
391	612.1	1088.8	1269.7	1459.7
410.53	681.95	1203.1	1326.85	1481.4
427.53	703.95	1239.1	1344.85	1501.4

Table 5. Selected Completion Time

Job 5	Job 2	Job 1	Job 3	Job 9
Completion Time				
136	183	239	278	295
257	317	429	509	534
922	1222	1582	1822	1922
922	1222	1722	1822	1922

922	1222	1890	2010	2010
958	1294	1960	2060	2087
1027	1435	2072	2150	2201
1687.7	2143.7	2706.5	3108.5	3279.5
1713.74	2195.78	2884.3	3235.5	3299.03
1736.74	2242.78	2940.3	3274.5	3316.03

4.3 COMPARISON WITH TOC

In Theory of Constraint (TOC), there using 3 variables as the main basic data which consist of due date, product revenue and material cost.

Table 6. Price and Revenue

Product	Price per Unit	Revenue
	IDR	IDR
Product 1	585,000.00	204,750.00
	IDR	IDR
Product 2	500,000.00	175,000.00
	IDR	IDR
Product 3	555,000.00	194,250.00
	IDR	IDR
Product 4	775,000.00	271,250.00
	IDR	IDR
Product 5	465,000.00	162,750.00
	IDR	IDR
Product 6	390,000.00	136,500.00
	IDR	IDR
Product 7	885,000.00	309,750.00
	IDR	IDR
Product 8	890,000.00	311,500.00
	IDR	IDR
Product 9	330,000.00	115,500.00
Product	IDR	IDR
10	255,000.00	89,250.00

There are normal working hour schedule, for the first scheduling before running TOC in Table 4.

Table 7. Normal Working Hour

	Working Hour	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Not-Over Time	08.00-08.30	Preprare								
	08.30-09.00									
	09.00-09.30									

	09.30-10.00									
	10.00-10.30									
	10.30-11.00									
	11.30-12.00									
	12.00-13.00	Pray								
	13.00-13.30									3316
	13.30-14.00									
	14.30-15.00									
	15.00-15.15	Pray								
	15.15-16.00									
Over Time	16.00-17.00									
	17.00-18.00									

According to Table 4, the calculation of NEH scheduling with the normal working time needs 9 days. Due date to finished 10 products are 8 days which had constraints in the scheduling with 2 tardiness on job 3 and job 9 with lateness respectively is 1 day. Industrial batik SMEs had disadvantageous because of the lateness on job 9 and job 3, with disadvantageous respectively up to Rp. 7,575,750.00 for job 3 and Rp. 1,963,500.00 for job 9. Therefore, total of disadvantageous which caused by the production lateness is Rp. 9,539,250.00.

Table 8. Overtime Machines

Over Time	Machine				
1 st Day	Cutting	Buttoning	Ironing	Packing	Sewing
2 nd Day	Itik-itik	Sewing	Buttoning		
3 rd Day	QC	Buttoning	Ironing	Itik-itik	Sewing
4 th Day	Obras	Buttoning	Ironing	Packing	Sewing
5 th Day	Itik-itik	Ironing	Ironing		
6 th Day	Buttoning				
7 th Day	Buttoning				

According to Table 5, it can be known there needs overtime machine process during 7 days and their needs the additional overtime machines process.

Table 9. Overtime Workers

	Amount of Workers					Total
	Overtime					
1 st Day	4	2	2	1	22	31
2 nd Day	1	22	2			25
3 rd Day	2	2	2	1	22	29
4 th Day	4	2	2	1	22	31
5 th Day	1	2	2			5
6 th Day	2					2
7 th Day	2					2
	Total					125

For Table 6, it can be known for each overtime machines process, there also needs overtime workers for respectively machines. Therefore, to decrease the product loss which unfulfilled, there can be implemented overtime schedule which shown in Table 7.

Table 10. Overtime Schedule

	Working Hour	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Not-Overtime	08.00-08.30	Prepare							
	08.30-09.00								
	09.00-09.30								
	09.30-10.00								
	10.00-10.30								
	10.30-11.00								
	11.30-12.00								
	12.00-13.00	Pray							
	13.00-13.30								
	13.30-14.00								
	14.30-15.00								
	15.00-15.15	Pray							
15.15-16.00									
Over Time	16.00-17.00	Overtime							
	17.00-18.00								

Based on the above table, we can know this industrial batik SME’s can implement overtime to the workers for 1-2 hours in a day. It caused the day of working hour only 7 days and there will be overtime cost for 1 hour overtime equal IDR 35,000.00 and the next multiplies. Thus, because of there are 125 workers, this SME’s can implement this overtime system through 125 workers. Therefore, this SME’s needs to pay the overtime cost to all of their workers around IDR 4,375,000.00. Therefore, because of the comparison among disadvantageous and the overtime cost very high, it will be better if this batik industry implements overtime cost to gain the high revenue.

CONCLUSION

According to the above analysis, the researcher can conclude that:

1. CDS methods have the smallest makespan up to 3398.4 minutes. Then NEH methods have the smallest makespan up to 3316.03 minutes also. Therefore, the researcher can conclude that NEH is the best method to minimize the makespan. According to the calculation, it can be known that by implement NEH method it can be thrift up to 2.42%.
2. The normal working hour (non-TOC) has result 9 days then the total of product loss which unfulfilled is IDR 9,539,250.00. Besides that, overtime scheduling (after implement TOC) there are implement 8 days and overtime cost for 125 workers up to IDR 4,375,000.00.

FUTURE RESEARCH

In the future research, there need to identify the process by implement lean manufacturing before calculate CDS and NEH.

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